

Localised Augmentation for Medical Image Datasets

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Abstract

Elastic deformation is a common technique for data augmentation in medical imaging, as it results in smooth distortions that improve model generalisation. However, when applied globally, it can lead to anatomically implausible changes and result in high computational costs. In this project, a localised elastic deformation method is proposed that restricts the transformations to the region of interest (ROI), making the augmentations more realistic and efficient. This approach was evaluated on the CBIS-DDSM dataset for breast lesion segmentation using convolutional neural networks. Performance was measured with Dice and Jaccard scores and supported by statistical tests. In the end, the results show that localized deformation improves the precision of the segmentation, increasing Dice by +11.43% and IoU by +7.88% over the baseline.

1. Introduction

Medical images are usually interpreted by trained professionals such as physicians and radiologists to detect diseases, injuries, and other medical conditions and in many cases, additional procedures, such as biopsies, are required to confirm the diagnosis. Machine learning methods have become valuable tools in medical imaging since they make it possible to perform parts of the analysis process semi- or fully automatically and help experts to make faster, more accurate, and more consistent decisions (Tsuneki, 2022).

In particular, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are often used for medical tasks such as im-

age segmentation, classification, and the detection of lesions, tumours or abnormal tissues. Although CNNs often perform better than traditional machine learning methods, such as support vector machines, random forests, and logistic regression, developing models that are robust and generalise well remains a challenge (Litjens et al., 2017). This is because CNNs require large and diverse training datasets to perform well in different scenarios. Unfortunately, it is difficult to collect such datasets in the medical field.

Medical imaging datasets are often subject to limitations due to a combination of ethical, logistical and technical constraints. Access to patients with certain diseases can be scarce, and data protection regulations such as the GDPR restrict the sharing of identifiable medical data (Litjens et al., 2017; Gupta et al., 2022). Obtaining high quality images is also complicated by the limited number of imaging devices available in some areas and the difficulty of collecting data on different population groups to ensure representativeness (Mehrabani et al., 2021). In addition, annotating medical images is a major challenge as, unlike natural images, it requires the input of professionals such as radiologists, making the process both time-consuming and costly. These factors contribute to the fact that there are few large, high-quality, and well-annotated datasets, resulting in an unbalanced and limited dataset, that can lead to overfitting, where the model performs well on the training data but has poor generalisation to unseen data, leading to inaccurate results when training deep learning models.

To overcome these challenges, data augmentation is often used to artificially expand and diversify training datasets (Garcea et al., 2023; Litjens et al., 2021), and

conventional augmentation techniques such as flipping, rotating, scaling, and intensity adjustments are commonly used (Goceri, 2023). However, these methods often struggle to capture realistic anatomical and pathological variations. To better simulate tissue variability, more advanced approaches such as elastic deformation have been proposed (Ronneberger et al. (2015) to improve the general performance. Even so, when applied globally, elastic transformations can lead to unrealistic distortions throughout the image, even in areas outside the region of interest (ROI), which compromises anatomical plausibility.

In order to reduce these limitations, a novel method based on localised elastic deformation is proposed. This approach focusses the deformation specifically on the region of interest (ROI), allowing for more anatomically realistic variations without altering irrelevant areas of the image to improve the robustness of the model while reducing the computational cost of training. As illustrated in Figure 1, the local elastic deformation restricts these transformations to the ROI, resulting in distortions that better reflect realistic anatomical variations compared to the global approach.

Experiments with the CBIS-DDSM dataset (Lee et al., 2019), which contains mammographic patches centred on annotated lesions, show that this approach of localised elastic deformation can significantly improve model training. By generating diverse and anatomically plausible variations specifically centred on regions of interest, the method helps deep learning models to better generalise to unseen cases, leading to improved performance and robustness, while avoiding unrealistic distortions in non-relevant regions of the images. Furthermore, by restricting the deformation to the lesion regions, the computational effort is reduced compared to applying transformations to the entire image, making the augmentation process more efficient during training. Overall, this strategy provides a practical solution to the challenges associated with limited and unbalanced medical imaging datasets, and supports the development of more reliable and clinically applicable models.

2. Related Work

Data augmentation plays a crucial role in overcoming the limited data availability in medical imaging, especially in CNN training (Kebaili et al., 2023). To improve its performance on medical images, recent

Figure 1. Examples of deformation augmentations applied with identical parameters for both elastic transformations
Upper row: The original image and the corresponding mask.
Middle row: Global elastically deformed image and mask.
Bottom row: Local elastically deformed image and mask.

studies emphasise the widespread use of traditional data augmentation techniques (Goceri, 2023). These methods include rotation to simulate different orientations, mirroring to promote feature invariance, scaling to achieve size invariance, translation to mimic the motion of objects, and brightness/contrast adjustment to replicate different imaging conditions (Cossio, 2023). Figure 2 illustrates their visual effects.

These spatial transformations are preferred because of their simplicity and their ability to improve model generalisation. Several studies have investigated the effectiveness of these methods in various medical imaging modalities and tasks. For example, research has shown that techniques such as flipping, resizing, and zooming can improve classification performance in different organ systems. However, their effect depends on the imaging modality and the clinical context (Goceri, 2023). Other studies focusing on CT and MRI datasets also concluded that cropping, padding, and simple geometric inversions are still among the most commonly used augmentations, mainly because they are easy to

implement and have a low risk of introducing visual artefacts (Garcea et al., 2023).

While these transformations help to standardise the inputs and simulate different viewpoints, they are not sufficient to model the complex, non-linear deformations that biological tissues undergo, especially under pathological conditions.

Figure 2. Examples of common data augmentation techniques applied to a mammographic image. These include rotating, flipping, zooming, affine transformations, and intensity variations. An additional elastic deformation based on grid distortion is also shown to simulate non-rigid anatomical variations

Elastic deformation is widely used in medical image analysis as it can simulate realistic tissue variations (Ronneberger et al., 2015). In contrast to rigid geometric transformations, it produces smooth, non-rigid shape changes by applying random displacement fields that are typically smoothed with Gaussian filters, resulting in anatomically plausible variations (Hatamizadeh et al., 2023). However, in certain applications such as brain tumour segmentation, excessive elastic deformation can lead to noise and degrade performance by generating unrealistic synthetic images, especially if the lesions are not connected to the surrounding anatomy (Nalepa et al., 2019).

A common implementation of elastic deformation uses B-spline interpolation, a well-established method in medical imaging for modelling smooth, non-rigid spatial transformations. B-splines are polynomial basis functions in piecewise order that provide a computationally efficient way to interpolate displacement fields (de Boor, 1978; Piegl and Tiller, 1997).

In ophthalmological imaging, elastic deformation

has been applied to optical coherence tomography (OCT) images to extend datasets for the detection of diabetic macular oedema. In the study by Bar-David et al (Bar-David et al., 2021), OCT scans were deformed with increasing intensity ($\sigma = 1-18$), and then assessed by retinal specialists. For low-intensity deformations ($\sigma = 1-6$), the rate at which reviewers did not identify the altered images as artificial ranged from 71% to 77%, suggesting that these magnifications were clinically indistinguishable. In contrast, medium ($\sigma = 7-12$) and high intensity levels led to a significant decrease in perceived realism. A follow-up experiment with deep learning confirmed that the use of low to medium deformations ($\sigma \leq 9$) improved segmentation performance without compromising clinical validity.

Similarly, elastic deformation was incorporated into an augmentation pipeline for digitised mammograms to perform segmentation using a U-Net architecture (Ronneberger et al., 2015), along with horizontal mirroring, zooming and resizing. Their model achieved a sensitivity of 92.32%, a specificity of 80.47%, a precision of 85.95%, a Dice coefficient of 79.39%, and an AUC of 86.40. These results show that the combination of elastic deformation with conventional techniques can improve the data diversity and robustness of the model without significantly increasing the complexity of the training.

Although elastic deformation effectively introduces smooth variations, it can still be limited in modelling highly localised or context-dependent anatomical anomalies, especially if these are not well captured by global displacement fields. For this reason, other augmentation strategies have been explored in the literature. Generative adversarial networks (GANs) can synthesise new realistic images by learning complex data distributions, but their training is computationally intensive and can suffer from instability or artefact formation (Frid-Adar et al., 2018). Similarly, patch-based methods such as CutMix and Mixup have shown improvements in classification tasks by promoting generalisation (Yun et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2018), but their utility in segmentation tasks remains limited due to their potential to distort anatomical boundaries (Shorten and Khoshgoftaar, 2019). Compared to these approaches, elastic deformation, especially when localised, remains a computationally efficient and anatomically meaningful technique, that is particularly well suited for dense

prediction tasks such as medical image segmentation.

Figure 3. Visualisation of elastic B-spline deformation grids. **Left:** original control point grid. **centre:** global elastic deformation. **Right:** localised elastic deformation applied to a selected region of interest.

3. Methodology

The proposed methodology consists of four main steps: preprocessing mammography images, applying data augmentation strategies, designing and training a segmentation model, and evaluating its performance. Figure 4 illustrates the entire pipeline.

Figure 4. Overview of the proposed pipeline

3.1. Preprocessing

The high-resolution CBIS-DDSM images were standardised to ensure consistency and enable robust training. Pre-processing steps included resizing the images to 256×256 pixels, normalising pixel intensities to the range $[-1, 1]$, converting to tensors, cropping around the ROI to remove irrelevant data, and applying contrast enhancement with CLAHE to improve the visibility of the lesions and create uniform inputs for the segmentation network.

3.2. Segmentation System

The segmentation network performs a pixel-wise classification to detect lesions. As a one-class problem, the output $\hat{Y} \in [0, 1]^{H \times W}$ represents the probability of the

presence of a lesion at each pixel. A U-net architecture (Ronneberger et al., 2015) was used, which utilises an encoder-decoder structure with skip connections to obtain spatial details and contextual information.

3.3. Elastic Deformation

Elastic deformation introduces realistic, non-rigid variability. A coarse grid of control points is defined over the image, each of which is assigned a random displacement vector. These displacements are interpolated with B-splines to form a dense, smooth displacement field \mathbf{D} . The field is further smoothed with a Gaussian kernel of standard deviation σ , and each pixel $\mathbf{p} = (x, y)$ is mapped to $\mathbf{p}' = \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p})$, preserving continuity and anatomical plausibility.

Lower σ values result in subtle, localised distortions, while higher values produce a more pronounced distortion. The displacement at each pixel is calculated as a weighted sum of neighbouring control points, with weights determined by B-spline basis functions, that give more influence to nearby points (Rueckert et al., 1999):

$$\mathbf{D}(x, y) = \sum_i \sum_j B_i(u) B_j(v) \mathbf{d}_{i,j},$$

where B_i and B_j are B-spline basis functions that are evaluated at normalised coordinates u and v . An example transformation is shown in Figure 3.

3.4. Localised Elastic Deformation

To restrict deformations to lesion areas, the displacement field is modulated by a spatial weighting function $w(\mathbf{p})$, derived from the Gaussian smoothing of the lesion mask. The localised displacement field is calculated as follows

$$\mathbf{D}_{loc}(\mathbf{p}) = w(\mathbf{p}) \cdot \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{p}),$$

this ensures that the deformations decrease with distance from the lesion, and that only pixels within the lesion mask are affected.

3.5. Loss Function

The segmentation network was trained with a composite loss function that combines binary cross entropy (BCE) and Dice loss, and captures both the pixel-wise accuracy and the overall overlap between the predicted mask and ground truth:

$$\mathcal{L} = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{BCE} + (1 - \alpha) \mathcal{L}_{Dice}, \quad (1)$$

where:

- **Binary Cross Entropy** (\mathcal{L}_{BCE}) measures the difference per pixel between the predicted probabilities \tilde{Y} and the binary ground truth Y , which promotes accurate classification at each pixel.
- **Dice loss** (\mathcal{L}_{Dice}) focuses on the overlap between predicted and ground-truth mask, which is especially useful for segmentation of small or irregular lesions. It is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{Dice} = 1 - \frac{2 \sum_{x,y} Y_{x,y} \tilde{Y}_{x,y}}{\sum_{x,y} Y_{x,y} + \sum_{x,y} \tilde{Y}_{x,y} + \epsilon}. \quad (2)$$

Here:

- Y is the binary ground truth mask (1 for lesion pixels, otherwise 0).
- \tilde{Y} is the predicted probability map (values between 0 and 1).
- ϵ is a small constant that is added to prevent division by zero.

The weighting factor α enables a balance between the two terms: a higher α emphasises the pixel-wise accuracy (BCE), while a lower α puts the spatial overlap (Dice) in the foreground. This combination ensures that the network learns both precise boundaries and correct coverage of the lesions.

3.6. Evaluation Metrics

Dice Coefficient: The Dice coefficient measures the overlap between the predicted mask \tilde{Y} and the ground truth mask Y .

$$\text{Dice} = \frac{2|P \cap G|}{|P| + |G|}$$

where P and G are the predicted and true masks, respectively.

Intersection over Union (IoU): IoU (Jaccard index) shows how much the predicted mask and the true mask overlap. It is calculated by dividing the area in which the two match (overlap) by the total area covered by one of the two masks (union). Higher values mean better overlap.

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{|P \cap G|}{|P \cup G|}$$

Together, these metrics provide a comprehensive assessment of both the marginal alignment and the overall coverage of the segmented regions.

4. Experiments

This section describes the experimental setup in detail, including the preparation of the dataset, the augmentation pipelines, the configuration of the model training, and the evaluation methodology.

4.1. Dataset

Experiments were performed on the CBIS-DDSM dataset (Lee et al., 2017), a curated digital mammography collection containing radiologist-annotated lesions and pathology-confirmed diagnoses. It was restricted to mass lesions to reduce within-class variation and avoid confounding effects due to different lesion morphologies such as calcifications. Each sample contains a single channel DICOM mammogram and a pixel-level binary mask delineating the lesion and following the pre-processing pipeline described in section 3, each image was:

1. Cropped to a square region of interest (ROI) centred on the annotated lesion.
2. Intensity normalised to $[0, 1]$.
3. Resampled to 256×256 to make it suitable for U-Net input.

Finally, the dataset was split into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) sets.

4.2. Augmentation Configurations

Five augmentation methods applied were exclusively evaluated during training to investigate their effects on the performance.

1. **No augmentation:** In this baseline scenario, raw clipped regions of interest (ROIs) were used without any transformation. This scenario serves as a reference to quantify the effectiveness of the subsequent augmentation strategies. The exclusive use of raw ROIs ensures that the model learns the features directly from the distribution of the dataset, but may lead to overfitting due to limited variability.
2. **Simple Augmentation:** Conventional augmentation techniques were used to introduce slight variations

in image orientation and scale, such as random horizontal reflections ($p = 0.5$), rotations at small angles ($\pm 5^\circ$), and adjustments of contrast and brightness. These extensions simulate the position and image variations that are common in clinical imaging, and thus improve the robustness of the model.

3. **Regular Elastic (Global B-spline):** In this method, a B-spline deformation is applied to the entire image, altering the global tissue structure. The regular elastic deformation leads to non-linear spatial variations, and forces the model to learn invariant features with respect to the tissue morphology. The deformation is controlled by global control points with hyperparameters α and σ and spacing to manage the intensity and smoothness.
4. **Localised Elasticity (ROI-based B-spline):** To preserve the overall structure of the breast while still achieving shape variability, elastic deformation was limited to the ROI. This localised augmentation ensures realistic tissue deformation and prevents the model from learning unwanted global distortions. Parameters such as α , σ , and spacing were scaled relative to the size of the lesion, to ensure an appropriate intensity of deformation.
5. **Simple + Localised Elastic:** Finally, the combination of simple augmentations with localised B-spline warping maximises lesion-specific variability while maintaining overall anatomical fidelity. This procedure is particularly suitable for lesion segmentation, as it introduces subtle shape variations without compromising the global breast structure. In the experiments, this strategy often yielded the highest Dice and Jaccard scores, emphasising the importance of targeted augmentation in medical imaging.

Identical parameters were used for all elastic deformations ($\sigma=10$, $\alpha=6$, distance=46) to allow direct comparisons. Figure 1 shows representative results: The second row shows the global deformation, which often produces unrealistic distortions throughout the image, while the third row shows the localised deformation, which is restricted to the annotated region of interest, and produces more realistic and anatomically plausible variations while preserving the surrounding structures.

4.3. Model Architecture and Training

The segmentation model used was a U-Net (Ronneberger et al., 2015) with an encoder-decoder struc-

ture, skip connections to preserve spatial detail, a single-channel input (greyscale), and a binary mask output. It was trained using AdamW with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , a batch size of 32, and for 25 epochs on a GPU (CUDA). A positive class weight of 3.0 was applied in the BCE loss. Hyperparameters were selected through preliminary validation experiments, monitoring Dice and IoU for stability and performance.

For the elastic deformations, the control point distance and α were set to 46 and 6, respectively, after testing different configurations to account for anatomical plausibility and variability in the augmented images. To ensure reproducibility, random seeds were defined for NumPy and PyTorch, and models were checkpointed after each epoch for later test evaluation.

4.4. Training and Validation Losses

To monitor convergence and learning behaviour, the training and validation loss curves were plotted for each augmentation strategy. In addition, the Dice and Jaccard values per epoch were tracked to visualise the evolution of segmentation performance during training. These metrics complement the loss curves by providing direct insight into the model’s ability to correctly segment lesions over time. Figure 5 shows an overall increasing trend in performance across epochs, with a slight dip around epoch ten, possibly indicating minor fluctuations in learning, but eventually reaching high values by the last epoch, showing the effectiveness and stability of the system.

Figure 5. Dice and Jaccard scores per epoch for the baseline (no augmentation) training.

4.5. Evaluation Protocol

Validation metrics were calculated for each epoch to monitor training progress, while test metrics were aver-

aged across all batches. Dice and IoU were also plotted at the batch level to visualise variability in the test set. The statistical significance of improvements achieved by the different augmentation strategies was assessed using pairwise tests on a per-image basis.

In addition to quantitative evaluation, a qualitative analysis was conducted to assess the realism and plausibility of the segmentation results. This analysis focused on segmentation plausibility, evaluating predicted masks visually by overlaying them on the original mammograms. By combining quantitative and qualitative assessments, it was possible to relate performance gains to the visual fidelity of the augmented data, providing insight into the trade-offs inherent in each augmentation strategy.

5. Results

The tables 1 and 2 summarise the performance of the test set for the different augmentation strategies. The hybrid approach combining localised and simple augmentation achieved the highest Dice score (0.7047) and a competitive Jaccard index (0.5473), representing a substantial improvement over the baseline without augmentation (+11.43% Dice, +7.88% Jaccard). These improvements were statistically significant, as confirmed by a Wilcoxon signed-rank test ($p = 0.0057$), suggesting that the improvements are unlikely to be due to chance. The localised augmentation alone also outperformed the baseline (Dice = 0.6882; +8.82%), although significance was borderline ($p = 0.0882$), suggesting a moderate improvement. In contrast, the Global elastic deformation strategy decreased performance compared to baseline (Dice = 0.6071; -4.00%), demonstrating that unconstrained global deformations can produce unrealistic variations that are detrimental to segmentation accuracy. Overall, these results show that localised, lesion-focused augmentation is more effective than global or no augmentation, in both improving accuracy and maintaining anatomical plausibility.

Visual inspection showed that localised deformations preserved breast boundaries and introduced realistic lesion variations. The hybrid approach produced cleaner lesion contours with fewer false activations, whereas global deformations sometimes caused elongation and boundary distortions, consistent with the lower quantitative performance. As shown in Figure 6, the predicted masks closely match the ground truth and

Table 1. Test results (Dice and Jaccard).

Method	Dice	Jaccard
Baseline	0.6324	0.5073
Simple	0.6698	0.5480
Localised	0.6882	0.5425
Localised+simple	0.7047	0.5473
Global	0.6071	0.4690

Table 2. Test results showing relative improvements over the baseline. Dice and Jaccard indicate segmentation performance. p -values correspond to the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Method	Dice $\uparrow\%$	Jaccard $\uparrow\%$	p -values
L+S	+11.43	+7.88	0.0057
Localised	+8.82	+6.94	0.0882
Simple	+5.91	+8.02	0.2910
Global	-4.00	-7.55	0.0712

illustrate the effect of localised + simple augmentation.

Figure 6. Segmentation example: input image (left), ground truth mask (middle), predicted mask (right) using localised elastic deformation + simple augmentation.

Figure 7 illustrates the segmentation predictions on a single test image. The top row shows the original image and ground truth mask, while the bottom row compares outputs from the baseline model (left side) and localised + simple model (right side). Notably, the localised deformation combined with simple augmentation provides more accurate lesion segmentation than the model trained without augmentation.

5.1. Discussion

Localised + simple augmentation is most effective

The combination of traditional transformations with localised B-spline deformation consistently yielded the highest Dice value with significant improvements over baseline (+11.43% Dice, +7.88% Jaccard; $p =$

Figure 7. Segmentation results for a single test image. Top: original image and ground truth. Bottom: predictions from different models.

0.0057). This suggests complementary advantages such as traditional transformations provide global orientation/contrast diversity, while localised elasticity introduces lesion-centred shape variability without compromising global anatomy.

Localised elasticity alone helps (borderline significance) localised deformation improved Dice by +8.82% and Jaccard by +6.94%, with a borderline value of p - ($\approx .0.088$). The effect becomes more consistent when combined with traditional transformations, suggesting synergy between global and lesion-centred perturbations.

Global elasticity is detrimental here The global deformation reduced Dice by 4.00% and Jaccard by 7.55% compared to baseline, likely due to anatomically implausible deformations confounding boundary learning. The qualitative artefacts observed on the breast outlines confirm this error mode.

Convergence and performance evolution Figure 8 shows the training dynamics for the localised+ simple augmentation strategy. The loss curves (right) show a steadily decreasing behaviour both during training and validation, indicating stable convergence without severe overfitting. In parallel, the Dice and Jaccard scores (left) show an increasing trend across epochs, confirming that segmentation performance steadily improves as training progresses. Taken together, these patterns show that the model successfully learns from the augmented data and generalises well to unseen samples.

Figure 8. Training performance for the localised + simple augmentation strategy. Left: Dice and Jaccard scores per epoch, showing a clear upward trend in segmentation accuracy. Right: Training and validation loss curves, illustrating a steady downward trend and stable convergence.

6. Future Work and Conclusion

In summary, augmentation strategies that preserve global anatomy while disrupting lesion morphology have been shown to be effective for segmentation of mammographic lesions. The proposed hybrid approach, combining traditional transformations with localised B-spline deformations, achieved the best performance (Dice = 0.7047, Jaccard = 0.5473), and resulted in statistically significant improvements over training without augmentation.

Future work could extend the proposed methodology in several directions. First, localised elastic deformation could be tested on additional lesion types, such as calcifications, and on other modalities, including CT, MRI, and 3D volumes, to assess generalisability. Second, the selection of deformation parameters (control point spacing, α , and σ) could be automated, reducing reliance on manual tuning and improving reproducibility. Thirdly, calibration and uncertainty analyses on larger test sets, together with feedback from clinicians on the realism of the augmentation, could improve both performance evaluation and clinical applicability. Finally, hybrid pipelines utilising modern backbones, such as semi- or self-monitored pre-training could be explored, while a modular and automated experimental framework would improve the scalability, traceability, and reproducibility of research.

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